

Amazing Evidence of God in Science: Tracing the Hidden Face of God Behind the Brilliance of Science

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Abstract: The link between seen and unseen, matter and spirit, was always presumed, but never clarified enough, leaving room for debates and mostly controversies between the scientific domains and philosophies of a different type; how could God, who is immaterial, have a place in science? Therefore, the logic of obtaining a result on this concern is first to see how different forms and forces of the universe have rationed between divinity and matter/universe. In this part, the scientists have differences of opinion on the idea of the universe and the existence of all its different elements and forms. How mysteriously the universes, Sun, moon, stars, the earth, water, animals, plants and human beings were created by the will of the Supreme from nothingness? In a way the Ultimate Being has gifted the universe/nature with the capability of ruling all, seeing everything and controlling, even determining facts by connecting all together with an Ultimate. An attempt is made to prove the undeniable truth of the Ultimate with the analogy of human body with its incomprehensible mysterious brain connections, unique and unimaginable designed DNA, the existence of a transcendent entity in the glorified science and the beautiful universe. Thus science emerges as a beautiful gift of the Supreme.

Keywords: DNA, Supreme Being, Ultimate Being, Evolution, Transcendence, Super Engineer

“Science offers a surer path to God than religion” - Scientist Paul Davies

Introduction

The Supreme Being could not exist within the dimension of space, time and matter, which is the dimension we exist within. Without Him to cause all things is to say that infinite empty space for things to exist within, mass in any form, gravity, energy, laws of physics, the passage of time, or any other such things were always there with no beginning and for no reason and that they had God powers to bring all things into existence even if it was by chance. God had to have been uncaused by anything and had no beginning. He would exist outside of our dimension. It was Him who would have to have brought all things into existence. An extraordinary venture was undertaken to demonstrate that the beauty and complexity of life cannot have come about by chance. If we think that the traditional Darwinian theory of random mutation evolution could have done the job of growing life on earth, ponder about nature and its true realities (Pandikattu, 2020). There is a mind at work out there. It underlies everything. His name is God. Here I would like to prove it by enumerating the evidence of God hidden in science.

The Magnificence of the Universe

Last few decades scientists around the world have been making discoveries which clearly showed that an intelligent designer is responsible for the creation of the universe. Many believe that the entire universe comes into existence out of nothingness. But in real sense nothing can bring nothing. Everything that exist must have a cause. The solar system is so brilliantly made. Everything in the universe is so balanced. Sun generated perfect energy for our life on earth. If sun produces more energy or less energy, then there is a catastrophe on earth. If we experience a drop of Sun energy by few percentages, then all the ocean would freeze. The earth is in exact proper distance from the Sun. If the earth was slightly closer to the sun or farther away, it would be too cold or hot for the life to exist. The size of the earth is not too big or too small. We also fortunately

have the right size of moon primarily responsible for regulating the tides on earth. (Michael, 2020) Thus, we find that how magnificently life is balanced on earth. If there is any slight variation up or down then life will be adversely affecting, perhaps life will be impossible. It is sure that there is an ultimate who designed and controls these celestial beings.

Existence of the Universe

On earth different forms of life is completely dependent on each other. For example, insects and plants such as bees and pollen bearing plants. If pollen bearing plants do not exist then the bees would not survive. Therefore, they must have come into existence at the same time. The ocean basins and atmosphere have a right mixture of gases. If these gases are changed in a way, then animal life and vegetation would die. The evolution has no explanation on why on earth and incredible amount of water and rich in oxygen. If the oxygen level goes little higher or lower, then our atmosphere will be completely unstable and explosive. Earth's atmosphere is transparent. This conveniently allow other planets, stars and eclipse. Evolutionists claim that solar system emerged from a cloud of swindling dust. Therefore, the composition of all the planets should be something similar but actually they are not. Some believe that complexity of life in the universe can be explained by the possibility that the alien races created. But we really believe that the aliens had the power to create the earth. But how about the size of the sun. The sun is very hot. Then how the aliens go about putting the sun in the center and constructing the solar system!

The Terrestrial World

The condition outside the earth, according to the evidence, too hard for the life to exist. For example, prolonged explosion to the cosmic rays and space can be faded. Just the temperature, poisonous gas, radiation, extreme gravitational forces, chemical

elements find it difficult for life to exist. Yet the larger number of evolutionists believe that life wasevolved on earth. Therefore, according to them it also must have evolved on other planets in the space. If such is the case, there must be alien much more advanced than us. Air craft more advanced than that we have, but we do not see any signs of such alien in the universe. Many studies have done searching for extra-terrestrial intelligence for decades scanning sky looking for intelligence. But they have not picked up even one signal from others space that would indicate alien race exists. All the gives enough materials to prove that there is a super controller in this universe.

Human Body vs a Super Computer

An adult human body is comprised over a hundred trillion cells of various sizes. Every cell can contain information equal to about 400 books. A cell is similar to a supercomputer microscopic size. These cells do multiple tasks. This looks as if designed by a super engineer. Looking at the working structure of the cells in human body, we can never understand evolution as ‘blind’, undirected process’ ‘without either plan or purpose’.

The Complexity of Human Body

How does reproduction happen if there was only male not a female? According to the theory of evolution humans evolved from lower animals, including fish in the water. Now the question arises: How the fish survived out of the water? How did the animals and human being acquire these organs and limbs? Evolutionists do not have clear answers to the development of the immune system. The evolutionists also have no satisfactory explanation on our extremely complex yet perfect precision on the body clot blood. Disaster can happen if blood doesn’t clot at the proper time at the proper place. If the blood clots at the wrong place for example, in our lungs or brain, we would die. (Roberts, 2014). The evolutionists have no satisfactory explanation to this. The human brain is the most complex matter in the universe. An adult human brain contains a

hundred thousand billion electrical connection. This is more than all the electrical connections of all electrical appliance in the world.

The one square inch area in the back of our eyeball contains over 137 million light-sensitive cells. All of which is wired to the brain. Human eye can clean itself. The eye has the capacity to focus automatically. If any distortion even by a slight degree you would see double. These facts are some of the evidences for the creation by God. We find clear traces of God's creative power and intelligence not only the designs of human beings but also in the incredible complexities of animals and insects (*Scientific Evidence for God*, 2015).

Decoding DNA

Scientists have found indications of God in the Code of DNA. What did they find in the DNA code that made them believe in the existence of God? As we know that a computer program is a series of binary numbers i.e. ones and zeroes. This sequence of 1s and 0s instructs the computer what to do. In the same way, all the functions that take place inside the cell of the body are controlled by an incredibly complex and extremely long code written in the DNA which is placed inside the nucleus of all the cells of our body. But now the question arises: How did this Complex code of DNA indicate the presence of God (Dean, 2015)? For example, suppose we are walking on a beach and suddenly we see a message written on the beach sand. The message is "God bless you!" Then what is the possibility that this message was just written by chance by the random waves. We will say, No, it's not possible, how these waves of the ocean can write this message. This message is a piece of information that must have come from intelligence. So it's not possible for us to neglect an intelligent mind behind such a simple meaningful message carrying information. So the point is, information comes from intelligence

According to Dr. Francis Collins, director of the Human Genome Project, one can “think of DNA as an instructional script, a software program, sitting in the nucleus of the cell.” Now if we see the complexity of the code written in the DNA, it will boggle your mind. The letters of the programming language written in the DNA are A,T, G and C just like the letters of computer programming language one and zeroes. As, what the computer will do is decided by the program placed inside its memory that may be hundreds to thousands of letters long. In the same way, whole functions of the body are decided by the DNA code having its copy placed inside each cell of the body. This DNA code is nearly 3 billion letters long and its instructions are written by different sequences and arrangements of the four letters A,T,G and C. A unique combination of these letters instructs the cell how to carry our extremely complex body functions. These 4 letters of DNA code A, T, G, C are actually names of four chemicals. These are Adenine, Thymine, Guanine and Cytosine that respectively stand for A, T, G and C letters. As 1100010101101 is an example of a computer program instruction in the binary language with letters 1s and 0s. Similarly AGAGTGGCTCACTCCTGAA is an example of an instruction in the DNA code written by using four letters A, T, G and C. Now remember the example of message written on the beach again. It needs an intelligent mind conveying a piece of information (Ballen, 2013).

A Super Intelligent Programming

How is it possible to neglect an infinitely intelligent super intelligence who has written that incredibly long, dense and complex code of 3 billion letters inside the nucleus of each cell? Who placed that code there? Is it just by chance? Do we know how complex this DNA code is? The DNA code contains all the information that makes up an organism. All the features that make you, every quality and trait that you possess, every chemical reaction taking place inside your body and lot more. This code is transferred to the next generations. That is the reason why a child

has many characteristics similar to his or her parents. No program has ever been written by chance. If you are a computer programmer then you can understand how much intelligence, concentration, creativity, pain and time it takes to write a simple code of just few hundred words if we want to get a task done by instructing a machine. Can that computer program be written without an intelligent programmer by itself by chance? No... So how can we think that this incredibly long code of 3 billion letters that is unbelievably complex and the densest storage of information in the universe can be written without a super-intelligence behind it? Who is that programmer? That must be no one other than the God itself. These factors eliminate the theory of evolution. Bill Gates says “DNA is like a computer program but far, far more advanced than any software ever created” (Gates et al., 1995).

Transcendent Entity in Science

If we smile at the universe, the universe would smile back at you. The reason for it lies in its creator. There are so many theories and arguments telling about the universe’s evolution. However, medieval philosopher Thomas Aquinas posed questions in his 13th-century book *Summa Theologica*, which presented several arguments for God’s existence. He observed that all worldly objects can change from potential to actuality—an ice cube can melt, a child can grow—but the cause of that change must be something besides that object (warm air melts the ice cube, food nourishes the child). The history of the universe can thus be seen as an endless chain of changes, but Aquinas argued that there must be some that initiated the chain, something that is itself unchanging and that already possesses all of the properties that worldly objects can come to possess. He also claimed that this entity must be eternal; because it is the root of all causes, nothing else could’ve caused it. And unlike all worldly objects, the transcendent entity is necessary—it must exist (Aquinas, 2018).

Mysterious Presence of God in the Beauty of the Universe

The universe is, in fact, a mystery. Then one who formed it might be still mysterious. Humanity is racing to go deep into this mysterious universe. Einstein compared the human race to a small child in a library full of books written in unfamiliar languages: “The child notes a definite plan in the arrangement of the books, a mysterious order, which it does not comprehend, but only dimly suspects. That, it seems to me, is the attitude of the human mind, even the greatest and most cultured, toward God. We see a universe marvellously arranged, obeying certain laws, but we understand the laws only dimly.” Einstein often invoked God when he talked about physics. In 1919, after British scientists confirmed Einstein’s general theory of relativity by detecting the bending of starlight around the sun, he was asked how he would’ve reacted if the researchers hadn’t found the supporting evidence. “Then I would have felt sorry for the dear Lord,” Einstein said. “The theory is correct.” His attitude was a strange mix of humility and arrogance. He was clearly awed by the laws of physics and grateful that they were mathematically decipherable. “The eternal mystery of the world is its comprehensibility,” he said. “The fact that it is comprehensible is a miracle” (Alpert, 2019). Therefore, God is a miracle in this universe. Without this miracle nothing exists; nothing can exist.

We need to explore the universe and its history a little more thoroughly before we can make definitive statements about its origins. Take birds for example. They supposedly evolved from reptiles. Now reptiles have a lung system, like mammals, where the air is brought in-and-out of the lung to alveoli through bronchi tubes. Reptile lungs: Air passes in and out, bi-directionally, through bronchi tubes. Birds, however, have a totally different lung structure. Air passes through the par bronchi of the lung in one direction only. How is the hypothetical half-reptile and half-bird going to breathe while his lung structure is being rearranged? Bird lungs: Air passes in and straight through uni-directionally. In other

words, is it possible for a lung to work at all if it is part-way between the bi-directional structure of reptiles and the uni-directional structure of birds? Not only is being half-way between these two lungs designs not better for survival, but the intermediate animal would not be able to breathe – he would die in minutes. Even in the evolutionary process, we can discern an all-pervading presence of an invisible power behind all the creation of this world (Ragnar, 2012).

Conclusion

Science, technology and artificial intelligence are all trying to negate God. However, from the above analysis, it is proved that God cannot be negated. Science is a golden gift of God. We see the world around and people around us as created by a Designer. And this is a Designer who has shown some amazing craftsmanship – including the unique design of each one of us. Call him the Ultimate, or perhaps something else. It provides a basis to understand ourselves, the world around us, and our creator. He has invisible qualities too. His eternal wisdom and divine nature have been seen from the beginning through what has been made. He has made His invisible qualities known to everyone. I stand with Sir Isaac Newton, to whom the Ultimate revealed the secret laws of the universe; the ‘father of modern science’ when he said that he could see the heavens through his telescope, but could enter them when on his knees in prayer. Thus, without any malice to the scientists who protonate the evolutionary views, the Supreme gifted science to the world. “For the Invisible things of Him from the creation of the world, have been clearly seen – both His eternal power and divinity-being understood by the things that have been made, so that; they are in excusable” (Romans 1:20).

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